

Cite as: T K John. (2007). Hinduism and Development (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune
Journal of Religious Studies, Jan-June 2007 (10/1), 27-50.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4266805>

Hinduism and Development

TK John SJ

Dept of Systematic Theology, Vidyajyoti, Delhi

Abstract: The author carries out a brief investigation of Hinduism's resourcefulness to face the challenges of 'development', on the one hand, and how the Hindu ethos is capable of taking a critical stand vis-à-vis the march of development that is a global phenomenon. The human process of planning, deliberation and making decisions need to be guided by a prioritization of values. The supreme value and concern is all that pertains to the nature, dignity and destiny of the human person. Full and all round development of the human person is a non-negotiable priority, and there is almost universal consensus on this. The human person is a body-spirit integral reality. Close on the heels of human development is the need for all that pertains to other needs of the person in society, the person in community, the person in the 'modern city'. Hinduism had made a remarkable contribution to the development of a great civilization. At the same time at a particular point in time certain degree of closure of mind and its exploration intervened that began to affect adversely the human person. Caste system was one major consequence. It impeded the pace of human development. The current society, along with the State, is engaged in pursuing development. The light of the fast growing human sciences could be focused on socio-cultural mores to help them become creative tools for the development of the country.

Keywords: Hinduism, development, closure, stagnation, regimentation, untouchability, people's movements, elitism.

Introduction

Four considerations have to be brought in while treating **Hinduism and Development**. First that India is a country of many religions and so the religious ethos largely determines the socio-economic mores of the people. Second, that there is a cause-effect relationship between the social formation and the economic dynamics and status of the country: both are marked by sharp contrast and distance. The lowest placed in the social structure are also the lowest possessors of economic goods, for centuries. Third, the not yet-properly scrutinized caste system has largely compounded and contributed to this anomaly. Fourth, the system that is operative seems to be marked by certain irreversibility. A bad mix of anthropology and psychology seem to be at work, apart from the callousness of collectivity.

A most distinctive feature of India is that India is proud of and enjoys a unique title and claim to being a land of religions. The recent plunge of this land into the global merge of economic streams now baptized as globalization with visions and values devoid of the ethical and the moral has generated much debate. Faster development is the proclaimed objective. The assumption behind this drive which is not yet scrutinized boldly and ruthlessly is that the western corporate capitalism will remove poverty and distribute well-being evenly and sufficiently for all. On to an already distraught social and economic system the elites of India have attached the economic policy and mode of operation of globalization stamped with inequality. We all have to be in the bandwagon and reach wherever the impersonal dynamics take us. Our collective memory is too short to recall that colonialism was the child of capitalism, and that western capitalistic model of development cannot but behave in the manner in which India was treated by the colonizers. The only difference is that this time it is the internal colonizers and capitalists that are the masters and holders of the keys, in close collaboration and network with the global contenders. We have a western capitalistic culture joined to the Indian caste hierarchical culture, a hard mix that is almost irrefragable. Both are devoid of what some world economists describe as economics with a human face. It may be useful to be forewarned that dive down into the pool by someone with insufficient

skill in swimming from the dive-board can bring either disaster or invite temerity. Will the **Hindu ethos** examine the dynamics of development at work in the country so that the Indian people will critically operate in order to evolve a thrust that will help everyone and help to keep our country on the right track— is the question. The following pages are devoted to a brief investigation of Hinduism's resourcefulness to face the challenges of 'development', on the one hand, and how the Hindu ethos is capable of taking a critical stand vis-à-vis the march of development that is a global phenomenon.

Here are some pace-setting questions. Does India know the roots and dynamics of development in the West that virtually destroyed religiosity in Europe and America and made many nations there disoriented and created "Iraq" as Nazi Germany gifted Spandau and Auschwitz to the world and to history? Will the land of religions survive 'development', if the phenomenon in the West is a lesson for all. One moot question too: is religion capable of contributing to development? or will it be an obstacle to it? Derived from the same: What role can Hinduism play in the realization of the dream India entertains of becoming a developed nation? If India has been developing is it because of religion/HINDUISM? or is it in spite of religion/Hinduism?

Some Christian authors (Christopher Dawson, Arnold Toynbee and others) have claimed that Europe is the creation of Christianity and Hellenism. The assumption is that there is a case of religion contributing to the making of nations. There seems to be much truth in the claim. The first phase of the making of Europe was by monks that fostered and nurtured centres of learning like Bologna, Sorbonne, Florence, etc. But with the birth of the empirical sciences and modern philosophy religion was left behind. Why? Is it because religion could not keep pace with the development brought in by science, technology industry and related developments. Although there is not much evidence of Christianity being practised in the West, yet, it is asserted, that the essence of the Gospel has been the very progenitor of western humanism. Can Hinduism play a role in helping a nation to develop integrally?

Japan is a 'developed' nation. But there is a Japanese stamp, so to speak, about Japanese development. China's partial withdrawal

from the world culture was to preserve and to promote what is the Chinese version of development. Their understanding of 'development' is not a mere copying of the Western patterns. What about India? An intimate link between a sound religious-cultural ethos and development seems to be the answer. India should decide what kind of development we need. Not an uncritical copying of what happens elsewhere but a choice that befits our national ethos and the needs of the people.

Indian religions, with the numerically larger Hinduism, are now faced with a major challenge: to run with the hare pulling the gold-plated cart of globalization and its progeny development. Will Hindu ethos, known the world over for what it is, promote the kind of development that befits humankind and eradicate problems like poverty, equally known the world over? Great Indians like Ashoka, Akbar, and the mythical Janaka of the puranas and the epics, are held out as examples of evolving state policy inspired by ethics and a spiritual vision. The essential core of the Indian religious ethos they tried to inject into political, social and other sectors of the state. Gandhi and Nehru of our times too are credited with such farsightedness and comprehensive vision. Nehru and Gandhi in own times tried to combine the essentials of the Indian ethos with the western and introduced and integrated what the two had drawn from both these streams. They were 'modern' yet Indians.

2. Conceptualizing 'Development': What is Development?

a. Development was about transforming the lives of people, not just transforming economies' stated Nobel laureate Joseph Stiglitz during his lecture in Chennai as reported by the Special Correspondent of *The Hindu* covering the session (*The Hindu*, Friday, January 5, 2007). The report further added that "Professor Stiglitz underlined the importance of India continuing to maintain its programmes for the weaker sections and the poor, for health and education projects and rural development measures and said that the state should not withdraw from these sectors". This warning from this informed economist is actually also the voice of the majority of the Indian people. That was demonstrated by movements and

trends in the country. Mumbai's World Social Forum and New Delhi's Asian Social Forum are crystallizations that illustrate.

Battling vigorously against this trend is a powerful minority that thinks differently and acts accordingly. It is involved in directing the nation in the opposite direction. Thus India is virtually at the crossroads. India is in a state of parting of ways. It is like the mythical scene of Kurukshtra: Duryodhana and his small but powerful holders of ill-gotten power and accumulation of wealth on one side ranged against the larger in their millions who are the losers in an unequal all-out war.

b.Uppsala based Dag Hammarskjold Foundation in its journal *Development Dialogue* ("Another Development," 1981: 1) argues that our understanding of development has to be widened and made comprehensive. The research document demands that authentic development should aim at the greatest improvement in the **quality of life of the people**. This takes place when all the possibilities people have to adequately satisfy their fundamental human needs are met. These refer to areas of a person's being having doing and interacting. Subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, leisure, creativity, identity, and freedom are a person's fundamental needs and these have to be adequately fulfilled. Development then should address these comprehensive needs of the human person. Religions would add one more to this list: transcendence. Obviously the State's understanding of development falls short of this overarching description of what ought to be the real components of development.

Hence the pertinent question: What then is *development*? And what is the role of Hinduism in the common task of development of India? The following nuances need to be taken into account when we use the term development.

c.Strictly speaking development refers to a dynamic process of actualization of a dream or a project or a potentiality, a journey from one situation to another, a transformation of something into something, an attainment of a stage envisioned, inbuilt and pursued. The best examples are available in abundance from a close observation of development in nature around us: the seed's development into the full grown plant that blooms blossoms and

become laden with fruits brimming with sweet juice and health-promoting nutritives. The journey of the power-charged white powder in the seed that sprouts, passes through the various stages like entry into the wet soil, growth and development of the sapling, maturing unto a plant or a tree, leading to the birth of the bud that blossoms into flowers, then the birth of the fruit with its many seeds within until the maturing and ripening—is a vital organic process of development. Here we observe the **vital/organic** process in developing and blossoming and blooming.

Close analysis of this daily event in all vital organic activities reveals the following elements:

First of all, it is the very nature or essence of the species that is being transmitted, is present in all stages, and manifests as the fruit. The fidelity to the nature or essence of the apple tree is preserved and operative at all stages. Hence continuity of the essence of the journeying subject is the first component in the process. The fruit that is the apple contains ‘appleness’, so to speak, all through the stages of the life-force dynamism at work. This is important for our understanding and critiquing of development and Hinduism.

Secondly, there is a goal or destiny towards which the journey is undertaken by the vital dynamism or impulses imparted to the organic process. The destiny inherent in the seed and which activates the dynamics of the journey is the fully grown tree, and full growth takes place when flowers appear and they blossom and produce fruit. Here is a genuine case of development.

Thirdly, there is the necessary sine-qua non role of the agents and ingredients in the forward and upward journey of the vital process. The moisture from water, the energy from the sun, the chlorophyll responsible for light absorption for generating the energy required for the vital process in the plants, are essential ingredients that contribute to the ‘development’ of the plant. The energy from the sun is also a catalytic agent that facilitates full development.

d. We take next another use of ‘development’. For this we enter the field of education. Those well-versed in the field of education trace the meaning to its Latin root, ‘educere’, i.e. ‘bring forth’ the various potentialities imbedded in the child in order to promote or

'develop' them and facilitate the full becoming or 'development' of the child as a healthy member of the society. Reference here is to the development of the physical, the mental, the affective, the kinetic, the artistic, the aesthetic, the transcendent and other potentialities and capabilities of every child.

eThe Christian understanding of the development of the human person will underscore all these, and more, because the origin nature and destiny of the human person are all traced to the creative act of God that creates the human being in the image and likeness of God. It is consequently evident that the term development can be applied to the human person, and collectively to the society, when the essential potentialities that constitute human nature is imparted the required stimulus so that actualization of these potentials take place.

First of all central to the concept of the human person is **reason**. When rationality is recognized with all its demands and human behaviour and social relationships are guided by the sine qua non of rationality we can say development is taking place.

Second, **freedom** is a non-negotiable second component of the human person. If the individual and the society of which one is a member honour freedom, foster freedom, and sufficient space is available for the legitimate exercise of freedom, development of the human person is taking place. Compulsion, regimentation, homogenization etc. are hostile forces.

Third, the **dignity** of the human person flows from the very nature of the person. If values like equality, fellowship, are enjoyed by everyone in a given society, it will be considered a developed society. The much honoured phrase, 'being and not having,' needs to be recalled again and again.

f.The expectation of this line of thinking is that the target of 'development' by the State **ought to be** the all round well being of all the citizens of a country, leaving none behind unattended. Availability of resources to fulfil satisfactorily the basic needs of all citizens and every citizen ought to be the set objective of planned development. Growth, advancement, prosperity and well-being are concerns of the State when it aims at development. Availability of food, health care, housing, literacy, transport, employment, security,

is part of the schemes aimed at development. Economics, industry, agriculture, technology, energy, natural mineral resources, labour, management, financial institutions, and other agencies are closely associated with development of the country. Rate of production, gross national product, growth in income, sufficiency of resources for meeting the basic needs of the citizens like food, health care, education, entertainment and relaxation and other items are considered as indicators of development. Space and freedom for the exercise of one's rights and live a life worthy of the nature and dignity of the human person are the crowning of such state policy on development.

3. Development as Conceived by the State

However the thrust and dynamics of development pursued by the State have merits and demerits. They are influenced primarily by the laws of economics where growth, production, and profit are the guiding principles and values. From the era of competition among mega corporations to that of merger in order to have greater control and greater profit, the trend is set. This powerful merger movements in industries and in trade climaxed in the much-debated globalization. It is a cultural mutation that has taken place. It is the global financial institutions that control and direct these trends. With the collapse of the Soviet Union and the imposition on the world of the unipolar imperialist capitalism of the United States, development is under the dictates of market economy, the child of globalized and globalizing economy. The human rights of peoples, the chief concern of the U. N. Charter, democratic culture and structures are subordinated to the demands of the market culture. Corporates have grown stronger over sovereign States.

a. What is the Criterion of the State and the Planners?

Growth is the central criterion. Growth in economy dictates other policies. High rate of growth, booming stock exchange, increase in benefits of free trade are enjoyed by people because a variety of goods non-available hitherto when control was strict, are available now. Indian mega corporates like Mittal and Tata are entering the international market and buying. Our information technology

competes effectively with other known and powerful companies the world over. We have a booming economy!

b. There is absolute reliance on the laws of economy and the favours and benefits of the market.

The laws and dynamics of the market are allowed to have their sway which will eventually percolate and fill the plates and cups of those below, eventually even of the deprived of India, neglected for millennia, we are told. Free enterprise encourages and stimulates private initiative which is key to economic growth. Rise in GDP is a reliable index of the health of the nation, it is held. India is credited with a booming economy. The Stock exchange and the behaviour of the shares market are the index.

These developments are commendable in themselves. But then how do the people on the other side fare?

4. Ground Realities that Need to be Attended to

But signals sent from a wide spectrum of the Indian peoples carry messages that need to be taken seriously in order to balance the picture. The nation has a soft belly and is vulnerable.

First, the already bleeding farmers' serial suicide, over 9000 in the last six years, according to official statistics, in at least four States in the South, seem not to disturb the planners and their pursuers. This is appalling since the phenomenon exposes the Indian rural sector, the mainstay of India's economy, as undeveloped or underdeveloped. Indian farmers for centuries lived in contentment though struggling hard against the vagaries of nature and other forces. But today desperation has overtaken them and the industry-enticing State seems slow to take note of.

Besides, conversion of prime agricultural land for mega factories, malls, IT colonies, has become part of the process. Industry that swallows agriculture in a country like India where the farmlands feed the people has fatal consequences for the future.

The farmers are suddenly waking up to meet the invading forces symbolized by the new child of globalization, namely, Special Economic Zones. Political parties with different ideologies fall in

line as in the game of ninepins. The suppression of peasants meets with democratic resistance. But brutal force is used by the State. Brutal police violence on the workers of Honda factory in Gurgaon Haryana, firing and killing of tribals in Kalinga, similar acts of state violence in Singur and Nandigram are among the latest indicators of the direction of development of which the State is only an obedient servant. Elected representatives toe the line easily forgetting the truth that they are to represent the voice and the needs of the people.

What has recently been called 'development terrorism' by the State, inspired by a fundamentalism in economics, a new and deadly kind of land grab has been planned unilaterally by the elites without the consensus of the electorate and pursued ruthlessly by people's representatives and by the bureaucracy. Livelihood is destroyed, land is forcibly taken away by the State at low price and sold to the Corporates at ten times or more higher level. In this process the till-recently observed laws pertaining to the tribal lands sale has been violated by the State.

Where does the land go? It goes to the over 250 special economic zones set up by the peoples elected representative at the hem of the State without consulting the people. More than 250 such Special Economic Zones have been sold out. Kalinga, Nandigram, Singur testify to the killing by the Indian State to satisfy the demands of corporates. People are expendable and disposable for the purposes of what the State decides. This is immoral and anti-democratic, and damages the current mode of ownership and livelihood.

Second, the tragedy among the farmers needs to be linked with the fast growing concern for ecology. The message that human interference with the laws of nature is fraught with very serious consequences is being sent repeatedly by nature but listening to that is yet to become effective. The experiment with seeds (cotton, rice, and others) seem to have brought us to a T-point. In order to secure fast and copious yields, disproportionately higher than the normal, chemically treated varieties of seeds have been supplied to the farmers almost under compulsion. The disappearance of hundreds of varieties of plants, cereals like rice etc are signals we can ill-afford to ignore.

Third, the cruel phenomenon of the Indian State evicting millions of Indian citizens from Indian cities on the plea that they are illegal occupants of space in the city is unpardonable. The State cannot consider such migrants as a law and order problem. The effort to develop Indian cities and make them be on a par with 'world-class cities' should be with due consideration for the rights of the Indian people. The rural poor have to give way to the demands of the new set of holders of power. The nation is haunted by this spectrum. Both the suicide by the farmers and those taking refuge in the cities show our planning and development vision and dynamics as flawed. Indeed it is a blot on our culture known to be humane. Who are these evictees? They are not outsiders, but Indians, all of them, people whose knowledge of their rights is limited. The evictees are those who migrated to the cities for their living, since rural situation failed them. The voluntary migrants are turned back, thrown out of Indian cities, to become forced migrants. Law, and not humaneness, is the criterion since the evictees are on illegal land in the cities.

Fourth, large scale sale of rivers to Corporates is also part of that scheme. Corporates will make money and deprive thousands of farmers of their use of water, agricultural labourers will suffer loss of work, fishermen, the boatmen and others related to the process of traditional fishing and living will be deprived of their occupation for living..

Fifth, displacement of population without proper rehabilitation in order to facilitate the growth of such corporations is taking place on a colossal scale the world over. From Hattia in Ranchi in Bihar to Narmada in Madhya Pradesh the record of the State as regards settlement is dismal because shabby.

Sixth, the growing naxalite movement tells the nation loudly that the governance of the nation since independence was faulty. According to the figures available from Ministry of Home at least 150 out of a total of 607 districts are already affected by naxalite movement. The non-fulfilment of aspirations raised during the freedom struggle days and promises made after Independence landed them in this situation. Land distribution has not taken place adequately. The functioning of the many State apparatuses in the rural areas leaves the villagers only in despair. The Naxalites intervene to

correct and to improve. Where the State failed Naxalites won. The unchanged status of the millions who are still landless strengthens the movement.

Seventh, the percentage of the illiterate Indians remains still forbidding. And without literacy opportunity for employment is very limited. Present economic and industrial development has added to the already swollen number of the unemployed. The number of the men and women who lack employment to live is staggering.

Eighth, large-scale borrowing from IMF and the World Bank and Asian Development Bank for the purposes of development is comparable to drinking sea water to quench thirst. Ramifications are such. It is the multinational corporations that are employed by the government at their terms for giant projects. Such steps further contribute to the already existing debt traps. To respond, other projects are launched in order to feed them. Drinking salt water is no remedy for thirst, wise fish workers know, but not the planners.

Ninth, welfare policies of early days have been abandoned in favour of the laws of economy. Financing welfare schemes are unproductive investment, managers of financial institutions tell the State.

Finally, a combination of illiteracy, unemployment and poverty has gripped those still lower than the middle class and those below with apathy and hopelessness. The benefits of development have not yet reached them. Drinking water, health care, electricity, transport, are among the urgent needs the far-flung villages are badly in need of. Their patience is exhausted.

In other words, commoditization of nature and of social relations has subjected everything to the demands of rude consumerism and the faceless laws of the market that attend only to growth. Bulldozing of the weak in the name of the demands of new economy and a devaluing of the people without resources (social, political, economic) is a major fall out.

From the strict understanding of the term development, the above black spots in human history are signs of undeveloped human thinking, being and relating. We can say that an 'undeveloped'

‘development’ is at work. We need to correct and move towards ‘real development.’

5. Some Factors Responsible for the Distorted Vision and Action

a. Elitism and Absence of Peoples’ Influence in Development

We need to take note of an important perhaps less noticed factor about post independent planning. The first Prime Minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, during his days of the freedom struggle had travelled through the country side, and engaged with the rural population. He was deeply moved by their situation. In his autobiography he describes the shock that this Eaton educated humanist lawyer and visionary had registered when confronted with the lives of the nearly famished ill-clad village folks living in their simple dwellings with little amenities. India is largely rural, he was convinced, and the rural population shows a picture different from the affluent elitist urban population. This experience of rural India, the greater India, had influenced much of his planning and decisions once he became the Prime Minister. In other words it was the voice of the people still ringing loud in his ears and their picture vivid and moving that was a major clinching factor for policy deliberations and decisions while he worked in the present day Teen Murty Bhavan in New Delhi. He introduced planned development with the people and for the people based on his perception and experience of the Indian people..

Gandhi, on his return to India, travelled through rural India and acquired first hand experience and knowledge of the Indian people. He listened to India. The planners and the industrial-trade magnates should listen to India and feel the pulses of the people and plan.

Are the Indian peoples’ voices heard and listened to by our present day planners and performers, is the moot question before us today. The shrill voices from Narmada, Kalinga, Nandigram, Sangru, Kalahandi, Netrahat, Koel Karo, ‘Noida’ Kheirlangi, are treated with apathy and contempt by the destiny-makers of the nation at all levels since they are considered blocks to the ‘development’ which the

neo-foreign colonies known as 'SEZ' will bring about for all the people of India!? Dictates from outside and from above and not the voices of helplessness from below rule development. How far do people's voice and needs influence those who design and execute the plans for the nation?

This takes us to further questions. What could be the experience and knowledge of the planners and economists about the actual situation of the majority of the Indian people? Minds shaped by the World Bank-generated economy and culture can be immune to shocks when confronted, if at all, with the life of the great majority of the Indian people. Ambedkar had the fire within. That fire was born of his bitter experiences of humiliation as a dalit. This fire, combined with profound scholarship, gave him the drive to battle ceaselessly for the socially transforming steps he envisaged for India. But are the majority of administrators, bureaucrats, and planners that come from the affluent classes able to register the anxiety and anguish of villagers of the caste-affected rural India? For instance, the Musahars of Bihar live on gathering the fallen rice from fields, rat-holes and the precincts of FCI go downs! Recently some States that under-utilized the fund allotted for the rehabilitation of the tsunami affected people returned the balance to the Centre. The news shocked the sensitive citizens across the country. Bureaucrats and administrators at the helm seem not to be fired by the wretchedness of our people. Another Nobel laureate Professor Amartya Sen had experienced the famine of Bengal in his early days, and that coloured his economics and helped evolve an economics with a human face..

The development of the human person and society takes place in the first place when all substantially inhibiting and enslaving constraints are removed and a correct vision is evolved. In India it is the Brahmins and those associated with them in sharing power in a graded manner that are planning for the country, governing the country, and making judicial pronouncements. **There is an inherent flaw in the very make-up of that governance.** How can the tainted clean the indigent! A major factor is the hardened and valueless institution of caste in India. Caste taints the enforcer of caste. India needs to be free of this major block to development. This needs further elaboration.

In India the major flaw in the development of the very concept of the human person intervened with the introduction of caste since its very essence is grading of the human nature and grading of the exclusion of those below. As a category this determines the mindsets of the upper castes and vitiates them, and afflicts those below. The malady affects the dominating and the dominated, suppressed and the suppressor, the excluded and those excluding, equally and adversely.

Since it is this dominant group or class that is governing the country, planning for the people, allotting resources for the maintenance of the various departments of administration, it is inconceivable that the caste prejudices will be left behind when planning and decision making take place. For example in the reports submitted to the nation after riots and orgies in Gujarat, it was made clear that community caste or class or gender prejudices vitiated the enforcement of law. The fact that what is now known as dalits as a body, all over India, are largely still kept outside the society and regarded as polluting and hence to be avoided, is a clear indication that 'development' in the full sense is not yet ready to be applied to the human situation in India. Economically, proliferation of goods is taking place and flooding the house kitchen parlour or even the bedrooms of the affluent. But human development and consequent social transformation is slow to take place.

b. Significance of Peoples' Movements

A distinguishing feature of governance in India is the space given to protest and to activism in order to attend to grievances the State is unwilling to listen to and address. It is to make up for that deficiency in democracy that various civil society initiatives in the form of peoples' movements, protest groups, and voluntary organizations are in the field utilizing the space available to them in the Constitution.

However, the future of this corrective presence and contribution to the democratic cultures and structures will diminish since the power in governance of the nation is still largely in the hands of the upper strata that are impervious, increasingly, to the voices of dissent. The best case in point is the campaign against tribals' displacement

in the Naramda valley. In spite of over twenty years of protests by the tribals, the upper class/caste combine has been consistently unyielding. The voice of dalits, tribals and other weaker sections have no impact upon the hardened minds of the ruling block. The power-holders in the society are unwilling to listen to them, honour their protest and consider their stand.

Below we need to trace the roots of this cultural malaise that intervenes in the process of developmet. We need to detect the perceptions, values and modes of deciding that shape the mindset. Religion has much to do with it since bureaucrats, legislators, judges, ministers, members of planning institutions all shape perceptions and organise actions

6. Hinduism and ‘Development’

In this land of many religions Hinduism is the largest numerically. Therefore its potentiality to shape the behaviour of the people is greater than that of the other religions. Hence Hinduism is called upon, as are the others, to play a role.

The expectation of the people is that religions, as the meaning dimension of a culture, are expected to wake up and redeem the situation in favour of the concept of development that will enable healthy and full growth of the human person, and of all persons in this large country of contrasts..

a. Hindu Humanism and Development

There seems to exist a close connection between the development thrust of a nation and the humanism of the culture. For the assessment of the situation of the people, planning, execution and evaluation are all conditioned by class/caste/gender and value bias and mindset. Humanism to a large extent is influenced by the world-view of a culture. Religion as the meaning dimension of a culture is a necessary, even major, component. Hence it is necessary that we consider the role of Hinduism for development linking it with the kind of humanism Hinduism has generated. A religion can influence the birth of humanism although other factors are also there to influence its shaping. For instance, elements of Christianity are present in what

could be called western humanism. But the western model of development is generated by humanism and also capitalism.

What could be the components of a humanism facilitated by Hinduism.

The following may be considered as components of Hindu humanism. It is not an exhaustive or researched data, but elements that seem decisive and significant are listed.

First of all, set against the Vedic cosmogonism and running through subsequent developments, is an evolutionary vision of all reality (*parinama/vivarta vada*). Accordingly there is a graded manifestation of different realities, inclusive of humankind, from one primal source. When we come to the human level in that scale there is the inception of the humans (in India) **caste-wise: brahmans** on top and **shudras** at the bottom. This original classification was later on modified to create another group, called the **panchamas** (dalits), outside the recognized the fourfold division. The origin of caste, however, is a much disputed topic in Indian anthropology/mythology combine.

Already, exclusion of one section of the human community has taken place, namely, that of the **panchamas**, the present-day **dalits**. The economic social and political powers and privileges begin to move away from them and move upwards towards the upper castes. Development benefits are only for the upper castes: land, resources, powers, privileges, rights. The lower we descend the duties increase and powers and privileges decrease. Dalits are assigned only abhorrent and despicable duties with neither power nor privilege, neither rights nor freedom. The era when this ideology was generated and matured could be now considered the most unfortunate. For, this is seen today as playing a major role in the development programmes and performances of the Indian nation.

Second, conceptually there is a mode of participation of all, especially of humans, in the nature of that one primal source, Brahman: (*tat tvam asi*, Aruni is told in Chand.Up.). Yet occupation for each caste is specified and there is no crossing of the fixed order. Rigidity and fixation as character traits are born and begin to mature and fossilize.

Life by prescription is introduced and walls are being created between profession and profession and between human agents.

Third, the axis of all thinking and doing in the early phase of Hinduism, known as the Vedic times, was **sacrifice**. And sacrifice was the key to the world of the gods on whom depended entirely the life of the Vedic Indian. *Yajet swarga kama* was the injunction ('Let the one desirous of heaven perform sacrifice') (*Artha Samgraha*, by *Laugakshi Bhaskara*). Sacrifice was endowed with power even over the gods. This power came from the *mantra*, the sacred formula uttered by the designated priest at the appropriate time. The performer of the *yajna* and the reciter of the *mantra* also share that power.

Performer of the sacrifice rises higher in the social hierarchy and hierarchy formation deepens and becomes rigid.

Fourth, *mantra* has **power, even over the gods**, because it is rooted in the Vedas that are of non-human origin (*apaurusheyam vakyam veda*). Vedas are eternal and have an existence of their own. The recipients of the Vedas, the *rishis*, and the dealers of the *mantra*, the priests, the brahmans, gradually began to be 'powerful' in society because they handle the Veda and the *mantra*. This religio-cultural phenomenon added to their social standing. Those without that power were kept at a distance.

Since the Vedas are sacred and liberating knowledge received from a realm beyond the human mind, they are received **obediently** and **submitted** to unquestioningly. This submission is extended to the recipient of the Veda, to the samhitas and injunctions, to the mores that were derived later on in the Sutra literature, and further down, to thousands of details worked out in course of time. This has resulted in the shaping of a mindset marked by fixation, rigidity in customs, beliefs and traditions. This uncritical acceptance has its unintended effect on the recipient, as well as on the community that receives them. What happened in this process was that the critical in the human faculty had to give way, and submission became part of that acceptance. At the popular level this led to a closure of the critical in humans.

However, critique of such a stand had been taking place periodically. The Upanishadic times, for instance. The Buddhist

revolt, for instance. The long history of Hinduism is seen as being punctuated by protest and stagnation, renaissance and relapse into traditionalism and blind veneration of the Past.

Manusmṛiti dealt with the Indian mind as those small men of Lilliput did with Don Quixote as we have in Gulliver's Travels: tied it down with prohibitions and prescriptions. Promotion of exploration of further avenues and of alternatives, exploration and discovery of the mystery and power in nature are yet to take birth. To tear asunder the binding ropes, and to break open the closed and frozen minds and to respond to the new challenges, powerful stimuli are needed. The demands of development need to be felt and met by our culture marked by this twofold features.

Fifth, the law of *karma* determines practically everything: your future, your present social economic and other status and fortunes. Ills of empirical life in society like poverty, misfortune, ailments etc are traceable to this law of determinism. And determinism ruled the roost for a long time. It did ravage many minds in all castes. Human science tools are needed to unravel and heal and restore.

There have been sprouts of insights demanding service and welfare of all like *lokasamgraha* (*welfare of the established order*: Gita 3,25)) and pauranic concepts like *ramrajya* (*welfare of all subjects—Ayodhya kanda*). Yet the fatal consequence of the law of *karma* reduced the impulse to serve others to minimum. To repair the damage it is not *karuna* that is needed but *nyaya Swadharma* dominated. We recall here its crude economic form as in Adam Smith's economic theory and how it has come to today's economic global policy.

Six, as a result of a dualism that intervened (*sreyas-preyas* (Kath.Up.); *purusha-prakṛti* (Yoga Sutra of Patanjali) and the growth of the institution of *samnyas* (life of the renouncer) an exaggerated spiritualism and other-worldliness grew and a downgrading of the empirical historical life, in spite of the later summing of Hindu view of life as guided by four-fold objectives namely *dharma, artha, kama and moksha* took place.

However, two counter developments kept challenging constantly this view, namely the *charvaka* view of life and the intermittent rise

and disappearance of dissent and protest against the institution of caste ritualism and polytheism etc. The former, with the entry of the affirmation of the sex-gift via *Kamasutra* of Vatsyayana, re-affirmed the value and legitimacy of earthly pursuit. Both these much-repressed and devalued systems have vigorously re-surfaced with vengeance in our times.

What had been the IMPACT of some of these features upon the human community need to be reflected upon. In the light of what has happened, predictability of what could happen may be possible. It is possible then to reflect upon this ethos vis-à-vis development.

The fact that the land and much of the resources of the rich land were in the hands of a very limited few was known to the patrons of religion. That means production and accumulation, though according to the rate and kind of the different ages, before the Moghal era, during the colonial period, were controlled and motivated by the interest of a few. Profit and accumulation of the profit guided further investment. The thought that others also should benefit, that others also have the right to the resources of the land, that others also have a share in the production of knowledge that was behind the systems of the times, was not part of the economists and resource-holders of pre-Moghul, Moghul, and British times. Still less was such thinking among the protagonists of religions. Is not this trend still continued?

We monitor diligently the Indian social structures. There is no mitigation of the rigour of the social hierarchy in India. The lower we go in the social hierarchy there is less space for the lower, and least for the lowest. The excluding culture has been operative at all levels in the new Indian governance culture. Maintaining this excluding mindset undiluted acts only against the incentives for social transformation, a major component of development.

Inter-dining, inter-marriage and other dynamic of levelling social barriers are only minimally practised. A sound humanism will advocate the rejection of social customs that are inhibitive of the development of the human person, and consequently of the community. B. R. Ambedkar was correct in holding that without social transformation freedom is in chains.

It is religion that was a silent bystander and approver when caste was shaped. It is so even today. Religion created the caste system. The same religion is unwilling to recast that religion in the light of the insights from the human sciences which reject these institutions as irrational and anti-human.

Caste system was and still is a social system which has led to the concentration of all powers in the hands of the upper castes and which deprives the dalits of these powers. Caste is also an economic system in so far as land and all resources are in the hands of the upper castes.

Caste also is a political structure. The upper castes largely constitute the upper class which even today, rule the country. They design the development plans for the people. They supervise their execution, although some from the lower rungs have succeeded in climbing the ladder – the so-called *creamy layer*. Three or four times anti-reservation fumes and flames warmed and burned Indian social landscape. The resistance to and protest against affirmative action for the low castes continue. That shows that the inherited social system and structure with its economic benefits and support system refuses to relent.

Development at the economic level without development of the social system, Ambedkar had warned, will give us only mutilated freedom and punctured dignity of the human person with all rights eroded. Ambedkar rebelled against Hinduism since he considered it a block to social transformation. Without social transformation economic development alone will benefit only the already beneficiaries of the inherited systems.

Under the inspiring and committed leadership of the first Prime Minister India embarked on a major national venture towards 'development'. And drawing inspiration from the Soviet and Chinese experiments planning became a major strategy for the development of the country. And the Planning Commission was created as the supreme body in order to design the development of the Indian nation. Similar approaches were made by other countries belonging to the so-called 'under developed' nations. Development became a global concern. International institutions like the United Nations created under its aegis departments like the UNESCO to address the

educational scientific and cultural and other aspects of the international community. World Health Organization was created to address in a focused manner the problem of health in the world at large. Because of the phenomenal growth and ramification of industrialization and to meet with the mounting labour problems the International Labour Organization was also created. Development became a major concern at the national and international level. It continues to be so even today even as the phrase 'under-developed' nations began to be replaced by 'developing' nations. But Nehru, the visionary, died a broken man because of the failure in execution. The reasons are clear:

First, the upper caste people have scarce experience of the degraded situation of the dalits.

Secondly, untouchability and pollution-purity fear keeps them away from the dalits not only physically but mentally, intellectually and emotionally. The officers keep them at a distance, as has been abundantly testified by the dalits.

Thirdly, the waves of anti-reservation campaigns have demonstrated to the

Indian people their conviction that the dalits have no way to regain their lost space in the society and to enjoy the rights granted by the Indian Constitution. These are major factors impeding the social transformation which is a necessary component of development

7. Closure, Stagnation, and Regimentation

Moderns like Subhayu Dasgupta (1990) calls this mindset as the ossification and stagnation of the Hindu mind. Sociologist G.S. Ghurye (1932) locates much of the consequences of such walled-in mindset in the caste system which according to him gave the Hindu society the look of a hive with its "snug living by surrendering the inbuilt fluidity and flexibility of the human groups. Human freedom and the colourful adventures and hazards that it might lead to were sacrificed to gain security, stability and the stagnancy of a hive" (Dasgupta 1990: 162).

The unhindered journey of the human mind in India began to get signals from promoters of the conservation of what has been achieved. Freezing of the mind and drawing of lines and building of walls began to emerge. Prohibition of the free wandering of the mind, and dominance of convention led to imposition of ban on innovative thinking and acting. With the advancement of thought fixation of the mind too caught up with the process.

One aspect of development is to promote and draw benefits for life from industrialization. True benefits from industrialization depend on the cultural ethos. Commitment to work and to duty is a major requirement. Religion and ideologies that promote consciousness of and application to duty are required. One unintended consequence of karma is minimizing this personal aspect and attributing behaviour or result or even temperament to an untraceable vague past action in a previous birth. This evasiveness and disclaiming would adversely affect commitment and production.

Red tapism, corruption, and non-performance are held out as factors associated with Indian bureaucracy. Failure of the implementation of national or State programmes for the people are traced to these negative traits in individual and collective behaviour. Religious and cultural ethos determine these traits in individuals. Religions promote purificatory rites to free individuals from guilt and culpability without linking rectitude and truthfulness, as well as personal responsibility. This caution needs to be carried into the offices, the laboratory, the mines and the factories. It is here that such beliefs and rituals block development. A ritual bath draws lakhs of devotees to the holy waters. On return to their place of duty does the devotee carry a purified ethics of work, duty and responsibility? If yes, our country will benefit immensely.

Concluding Observations

The human process of planning, deliberation and making decisions need to be guided by a prioritization of values. The supreme value and concern is all that pertains to the origin nature dignity and destiny of the human person. Full and all round development of the human person is non-negotiable priority, and there is almost universal consensus on this. The human person is body-spirit integral reality.

Close on the heels of human development is the need for all that pertains to other needs of the person in society, the person in community, the person in the 'modern city'. A major concern of the State is on this issue of development.

Hinduism had made a remarkable contribution to the development of a great civilization. At the same time at a particular point in time certain degree of closure of mind and its exploration intervened that began to affect adversely the human person. Caste system was one major consequence. It impeded the pace of human development. The current society, along with the State, is engaged in pursuing development. The light of the fast growing human sciences could be focused on socio-cultural mores to help them become creative tools for the development of the country.

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